

Utilization of Instructional Simulation in the Teaching and Learning of Sciences in Senior Secondary Schools in Ekeremor Local Government Area of Bayelsa State

Uchechi Doris CHUKUNDAH (PhD)¹ & Kate Tuotamunonengi ALIBO²

^{1&2}Department of Science Education, Federal University Otuoke
Bayelsa State

chukundahud@fuotuo.ke.edu.ng

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Abstract

This study investigated the utilization of instructional simulation in the effective teaching and learning of sciences in secondary schools in Ekeremor Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The sample of the study constituted of 98 SSS2 science students drawn from 1224 senior secondary schools students of 16 secondary schools in Ekeremor local government area. The instrument used for data collection was questionnaire. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions. The findings of the study revealed that graphic simulation were utilized to a high extent. Also, the extent of utilization of computer modeling and laboratory equipment's was equally to a high extent in teaching and learning of science subjects in secondary schools in Ekeremor Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. It was strongly recommended that science teachers should regularly use instructional simulation in science lessons, holistic use of graphic simulation, computer modeling and laboratory equipment's in secondary schools in Ekeremor, Bayelsa State to gain needed synergy.

Keywords: Utilization, Instructional, Simulation Teaching and Learning,

Introduction

Science has to do with the systematic study of nature. In addition, Esu (2004) defined science as a systematic, precise, objective way to study the natural world. Science is often an exciting and satisfying enterprise that requires creativity, skill and insight based on this Fape (2007) defined science as rationally structured knowledge about nature, which embraces systematic methods of positive attitudes for its acquisition, teaching, learning and application.

The major goal of science education is to develop scientifically literate individuals that are concerned with high competence for rational thoughts and actions. The objectives of science education in this country according to Maduekwe (2006) include the need to prepare students to observe and explore the environment, explain simple natural phenomena, develop scientific attitudes including curiosity, critical reflection and problems in the environment, develop self-confidence and self-reliance through problem solving activities in science.

In recent times, countries all over the world, especially the developing ones like Nigeria, are striving hard to develop technologically and scientifically, since the world is turning scientific and all proper functioning of lives depend greatly on science. According to Ogunleye (2006) Science is a dynamic human activity concerned with understanding the working of our world. This understanding helps man to know more about the universe. Without the application of science, it

would have been difficult for man to explore the other planets of the universe. Science comprises the basic disciplines such as Physics, Chemistry, Mathematics and Biology. The core sciences are physics, chemistry and biology with mathematic known as mother of all science.

In contemporary Nigeria, greater emphasis is placed on science and technological development. As a result, students are being encouraged to take up science-related subjects. Today, Science subjects such as Chemistry, physic, Biology, computer pervades literally every field of human endeavor, and plays a fundamental role in educational advancement. This is seen in all the technological advancement in the world today, which is because of scientific investigations. However, the issue remains that in most secondary schools in Nigeria, there is high rate of failure in the science subjects. Studies have shown that secondary school students are exhibiting low interest in sciences (Esiobu, 2005). This low interest of students in sciences has been traced to poor achievement in examinations. In our march towards scientific and technological advancement, we need nothing short of good achievement in science subjects at all levels of schooling. Unfortunately, achievement of students in sciences at the end of the secondary schools has not improved in the last decade (Umoinyang, 1999). Folorunso (2004) has linked poor achievement trend in sciences particularly to the lack of instructional resources in schools due to poor funding of schools. The poor funding of schools has hindered the head teachers from providing the science teachers with adequate instructional resources.

The National Policy on Educational (FME, 2004) emphasizes the need for teaching and learning of science processes and principles. The policy recommends practical, exploratory and experimental methods of teaching. In this regards, Okebukola (2002) stated that the basic tools that science uses in the learning of science processes are the instructional simulation. Interestingly, studies have shown that the use of instructional materials have improved achievement (George, 2008; & Nwagbo, 2009). Instructional simulation materials are wide varieties of instructional element, equipment and materials used for teaching and learning by teachers to stimulate self-activity, explore on the part of the students. A lab microscope for instance is a piece of standard laboratory equipment that enables the operator/user/students to produce enlarged images of small objects that are hard to see from a naked eye. Students can learn a lot with a good quality microscope, like a compound microscope, making their biology subject better and more enjoyable with a simple light microscope.

No doubt, we can use graphic simulation to enrich visualization and interactivity with active virtual reality of natural phenomena (Martinez-Jimenez, Pontes-Pedrajas, Polo, & Climent-Bellido, 2003). This is because simulations and various models help students understand scientific processes and mechanisms in natural phenomena. Computer simulation remains an effective tool to supplement teaching as to increase students' concentration level. Chukundah and Odibo (2024) agreed that photographic instructional package enhances students' interest and achievement in biology. The teaching of sciences without instructional simulation materials may certainly result in poor academic achievement. Poor academic achievement in sciences, inadequate motivation from teacher, poor incentives to science teachers, lack of adequate motivation from teacher, lack of adequate supply of instructional simulation material, lack of qualified teachers, and use of teacher centered instructional strategies, inadequate use of instructional materials and use of abstract standardized materials. Among these factors, teacher's use of abstract standardized instructional strategy is considered as an important factor in this study.

The thrust remains that the mastery of scientific concepts might not be fully achieved without the use of instructional resources that the students are abreast with. This is because most important

thing in science education is the practical side and hands-on training, especially in secondary schools, where the students gradually begin to embody their learning and use their observation skills, analysis, and conclusion (Chen, & Howard, 2010). The teaching of sciences without instructional simulation materials may certainly result in poor academic achievement. Folorunso (2004) observed that there is lack of adequate and appropriate instructional resources for effective teaching of science in schools. For Ibitoye and Fape (2007), the poor achievement in sciences was traced to poor usage of instructional resources for science teaching and learning, poor state of infrastructure facilities, large class size, poor teaching, use of faulty assessment practice, and inadequacy of quality teachers. According to Okebulola (2015), the poor state of laboratory facilities and inadequate use of instructional materials has constituted a cog in the wheel of students' achievement in science in the senior school examination. The verbal exposition does not promote skill acquisition, objectivity, and critical thinking abilities that will enable the child to function effectively in the society. This according to the researcher leads to poor achievement of students in the subject.

The report of West African Examination Council (WAEC) on the Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSCE) (2023) on student enrollment and performance in Nigeria by subject, grade, and sex revealed a persistent poor achievement of students in science at senior school certificate examination (WAEC; Chief Examiner's report 2019-2022), leaves one in doubt about the utilization of instructional simulation materials and teaching methods popularly used by the science teachers for the teaching and learning of sciences.

Statement of the Problem

Reviewed studies have shown that failure rate in sciences at senior certificate examinations are high. This could be attributable to a number of factors; one of such factors is lack or total absence of instructional simulation materials. In teaching and learning of sciences, instructional simulation materials play a key role towards concretizing learning. Instructional simulation materials make learning meaningful and help to improve student's academic achievement. However, these advantages of instructional simulation materials have not reflected in the education system because of the death of these instructional materials in our schools. No wonder, abstract and theoretical teaching of sciences that lack applications of science concepts in real situations, making learners lose zeal for sciences because they cannot connect the content to the real world (Memoir, 2016). Chemistry, Physics and Biology are complex subjects and so requires the use of instructional simulation materials for proper understanding of its concepts by students. Studies have shown the importance of the utilization of instructional simulation materials in teaching sciences, such as providing students with practice, engaging students, improving information retention, and improving analytical skills among others. Yet, the much observed neglect in utilization of instructional simulation in the teaching and learning of science subjects are too obvious to be ignored. Therefore, this study is geared towards finding out if instructional simulation materials are utilized in the teaching and learning of sciences in Ekeremor Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the utilization of instructional simulation materials in the teaching and learning of science in Ekeremor Local Government Area. This study specifically determined

- i. The extent of the usage of graphics simulation in the teaching and learning of science in Ekeremor Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.
- ii. The extent of the usage of computer modeling in the teaching and learning of sciences in senior secondary schools in Ekeremor Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.
- iii. The extent to which laboratory equipment's are used in the teaching and learning of sciences in Ekeremor Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

- i. What is the extent of usage of graphics in the teaching and learning of sciences in senior secondary schools in Ekeremor Local Government Area of Bayelsa State?
- ii. What is the extent of use of computer modeling in the teaching and learning of sciences in Ekeremor Local Government Area of Bayelsa State?
- iii. To what extents are laboratory equipment's used in the teaching and learning of sciences in Ekeremor Local Government Area of Bayelsa State?

Conceptual Review

Concept of Instructional Simulation

A simulation to Lateef (2010) is a model that mimics the operation of an existing or proposed system, providing evidence for decision-making by being able to test different scenarios or process changes. An instructional simulation, also called an educational simulation, is a simulation of some type of reality (system or environment) but which also includes instructional elements that help a learner explore, navigate or obtain more information about that system or environment that cannot generally be acquired from mere experimentation. Simulations are instructional scenarios where the learner is placed in a "world" defined by the teacher to represent a reality within which students interact. The teacher controls the parameters of this "world" and uses them to help students achieve the learning outcomes. Simulation-based learning is a form of experiential learning where learners are tasked to solve complex problems in controlled environments through replicated "real-life scenarios" (Lateef, 2010). Educational simulation is a teaching method that tests participants' knowledge and skill levels by placing them in scenarios where they must actively solve problems. The instructor defines the parameters to create a safe environment for hands-on learning experiences. The key element that differentiates instructional simulation from other pedagogies is the formal specification of a conceptual structure with which students interact to learn about relationships between concepts.

Concept of Teaching and Learning

Teaching is the practice implemented by a teacher aimed at transmitting skills (knowledge, know-how, and interpersonal skills) to a learner, a student, or any other audience in the context of an educational institution. Teaching is closely related to learning, the student's activity of appropriating this knowledge. Teaching is generally an intimate contact between a more mature personality and a less mature one which designed to further the education of the latter (Sun, Lin, & Yu, 2008). In its broadest sense, teaching is a process that facilitates learning. Teaching is the specialized application of knowledge, skills and attributes designed to provide unique service to meet the educational needs of the individual and of society. Teaching has been defined as engagement with learners to enable their understanding and application of knowledge, concepts and processes while learning is the acquisition of knowledge or skills through study, experience,

or being taught. Learning is a change in knowledge, beliefs, behaviors or attitudes; Learning is not something done to students, but something that students themselves do.

Empirical Review

Lateef, (2010) in his simulation-based learning noted that simulation is a technique for practice and learning that can be applied to many different disciplines and trainees. It is a technique (not a technology) to replace and amplify real experiences with guided ones, often "immersive" in nature, that evoke or replicate substantial aspects of the real world in a fully interactive fashion. He maintained that simulation-based learning can be the way to develop health professionals' knowledge, skills, and attitudes, whilst protecting patients from unnecessary risks, stressing that simulation-based medical education can be a platform which provides a valuable tool in learning to mitigate ethical tensions and resolve practical dilemmas. Hence, simulation-based training techniques, tools, and strategies can be applied in designing structured learning experiences, as well as be used as a measurement tool linked to targeted teamwork competencies and learning objectives. It has been widely applied in fields such aviation and the military. In medicine, simulation offers good scope for training of interdisciplinary medical teams. The realistic scenarios and equipment allows for retraining and practice till one can master the procedure or skill. An increasing number of health care institutions and medical schools are now turning to simulation-based learning. Teamwork training conducted in the simulated environment may offer an additive benefit to the traditional didactic instruction, enhance performance, and possibly also help reduce errors.

Rutten, van Joolingen, and van der Veen, (2012) carried out reviews on the (quasi)experimental research of the past decade on the learning effects of computer simulations in science education. The focus was on two questions: how use of computer simulations can enhance traditional education, and how computer simulations are best used in order to improve learning processes and outcomes. The study investigated computer simulations as a replacement of or enhancement to traditional instruction. Consideration was paid to the effects of variations on how information is visualized, how instructional support is provided, and how computer simulations are embedded within the lesson scenario. Extant literature reviewed provided robust evidence that computer simulations can enhance traditional instruction, especially as far as laboratory activities are concerned. However, in most research the use of computer simulations has been approached without consideration of the possible impact of teacher support, the lesson scenario, and the computer simulation's place within the curriculum.

Niyigena & Nzabalirwa, (2022) investigated the use of computer simulations as a teaching method for improving learners' performance in learning the concepts of plants and animal cells. This study consisted of 240 learners as respondents who were randomly put into treatment and control group. These groups were taught the same topic of plant and animal cells for two weeks. An experimental group was taught cell using simulations and a control group was taught without simulations. Biology achievement test was administered to both groups of students to check performance variation. The learners' marks were examined using t-test and the results showed that treatment group performed better than control group. Also, the results showed the significant difference in marks obtained by both groups at the alpha of 0.05 as test statistic = - 3.718, P-value=0.00<0.05. Hence, it has been proven that, using computer simulations in teaching and learning improves learners' performance. This is in conformity with Chukundah and Naade (2020) posit that computer animation instructional package is significant to student's achievement in ecology.

Mohamed, Abdesselam, Taoufik, & El Mehdi, (2021) carried study aimed to determine the effect of using computer simulation on students' performance in teaching and learning physical science, particularly the electrical Ohm's law. A sample of 182 students classified into two groups—experimental (92) and control (90)—from two middle schools in Meknes city (one in the rural area and the other urban area) was the subject of a pretest and posttest evaluation. The outcomes of the administered test to both groups of students control and experimental, were compared and analyzed using Student's t-test and the Mann–Whitney U test with Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The results obtained suggest that the experimental group register the best performances after the posttest than the control group. While no difference, in terms of performance, was signed according to gender in the experimental group, the urban students were more successful than the rural ones, with and without the use of simulations. In this respect, the study recommended using and practicing simulation software to improve and develop the performance of middle school students.

Ali, & De Jager, (2020) investigated whether the understanding of Life Sciences concepts learnt in the classroom have any influence learners' daily decision-making and lifestyle within the South African Curriculum Assessment Policy Statements (CAPS). They stressed that Basic Life Science knowledge should not only be acquired as head knowledge, but learners should also be able to put to use the scientific concepts and content knowledge in their daily life, especially when it comes to decision making and problem solving. They adopted qualitative case study, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 60 learners ($n = 60$) from Grades 8 to 12 in a High school with modern laboratory and educational technology facilities. Data collected were analyzed using the constant comparative method. The findings revealed that learners viewed Life Sciences knowledge as being for academic and promotion purposes only learners are not aware of how knowledge acquired in the classroom can be transferred so as to be useful in their daily lives as their learning experience is in the traditional way. They suggested authentic and real-life learning approach instead. Thus, promoting learner's personal knowledge construction as a result empowering learner with the ability to link the classroom knowledge to their everyday life.

Theoretical Framework

This study is built on Jerome Bruner's Learning Theory and Piaget's Theory of Learning.

Jerome Bruner's Learning Theory: Bruner introduced the concept of learning by discovery. Bruner is of the view that learning is effectively engaged in if the learner is giving the opportunity to discover facts by him/herself. Bruner argues that mere presentation of information will not enhance effective solution of a problem. The theory stresses cognitive effectiveness. Because of this, some referred to Bruner's theory of learning as Bruner's theory of cognitive development. Bruner believed that learning by discovery begins when science teacher purposefully (intentionally) create (present) a problem and present it to the students by introducing some assimilation: this occurs when a student recognizes a new situation that is familiar to one of the elements in the existing structure of knowledge (i.e. cognitive structure) and he/she easily assimilates it (Main, 2023).

Piaget's theory of Learning; Piaget's cognitive theory of learning refers to the stage theory of cognitive development. According to Piaget, children develop knowledge by inventing or constructing reality out of experience and thus mix their observation with their ideas about how the world works. Piaget observed that people of the same age level (especially children) have a similar line of reasoning. For instance, children of the same age level have similar line of reasoning or thinking. Children may make the same type of mistakes. They may have the same reasoning

process. This indicates that cognitive theory can be applied to enhance children learning in science and math. Piaget used the terms 'Assimilation' and 'Accommodation' to explain these views (Fallahi, Dell, Franz, & Greeley, 2017).

Method

Survey design was used for this study, this involves the process of conducting research using questionnaire to collect data. The data collected from respondents are statistically analyzed to draw meaningful research conclusions. The population of this study consists of all the 1224 SSII science students from all the 16 secondary schools in Ekeromor Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. SS II students were used because they are not in final examination class, so they are more favorably disposed to be involved in the study.

Ninety eight (98) students were drawn using simple random sampling technique. Simple random sample is a sub-set of individuals chosen from a larger set in which a sub-set of individuals are choosing randomly, all with the same probability. In simple random sample each sub-set of individual has the probability of being chosen for the sample as any other individuals. This sampling method is chosen because random sampling is a part of the sampling technique in which each sample has an equal probability of being chosen, and a sample chosen randomly is unbiased representation of the total population.

The instrument for data collection is a self-designed questionnaire titled Utilization of Instructional Simulation materials in Sciences (UISMS). The instrument was sectionalized into two sections, section A elicit information on respondent's demographics data while section B elicit information based on the objectives. The research instrument received content and face validity by the research supervisor and two experts from science education department in the faculty of education, Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. These experts validated the instruments in terms of face and content, ensuring: clarity of instrument to the respondents. Clarity of language, lack of ambiguity, appropriateness and adequacy of the items in measuring what it supposed to measure.

The test-retest method was utilized to establish the reliability of the instrument. The instrument was administered to science students outside the study. Two weeks after the instrument was re-administered to the same respondents, and Pearson product movement technique was employed to establish a reliability coefficient of 0.79 which is reliable enough. A letter of introduction was passed to the principals of the schools to seek approval before administering a copy of the questionnaire to each of science student and teachers. The instrument was collected the same day they were administered. The responses gathered were used for data collection for the research study.

Data Analysis and Presentation

The data analysis was done using descriptive statistics (Mean) to answer the research questions. 2.50 was the criterion mean used. Item mean of 2.50 and above was regarded as high extent while item mean below 2.50 was regarded low extent of utilization.

Research Question 1: What is the extent of usage of graphics simulation in the teaching and learning of sciences in Ekeremor Local Government Area of Bayelsa State?

Table 1 The mean and standard deviation on usage of graphics simulation in the teaching and learning

S/N	ITEM	SA	A	D	SD	N	Total	X	SD	Remark
1	Graphic simulation are used to display historical comparisons and relation between two set of data	60	30	6	2	98	334	3.51	1.73	Accepted
2	Graphic simulation are used to demonstrate trend and patterns in the teaching and learning of science	54	30	10	4	98	330	3.36	1.69	Accepted
3	Graphic simulation aid in the understanding of scientific concepts	58	21	16	3	98	330	3.36	1.70	Accepted
4	Graphic simulation are used in organizing information in science	63	19	12	4	98	337	3.43	1.76	Accepted
Grand mean(\bar{x})								3.42	1.72	Accepted

Source: Survey Data, 2024

Table 1 revealed that all the items (1 to 4) have means of 3.51, 3.36, 3.36 and 3.43 respectively, which were greater than the criterion mean (2.50). Moreover, the grand mean (3.42) was also greater than the criterion means. This opined that there is a high extent of usage of graphics simulation in the teaching and learning of science subjects in Ekeremor Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.

Research Question 2: What is the extent of usage of computer modeling in the teaching and learning of sciences in Ekeremor Local Government Area of Bayelsa State?

Table 2 The mean and standard deviation on extent of use of computer modeling in the teaching and learning of science

S/N	Item	4	3	2	1	N	Total	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
		SA	A	D	SD					
1	Computer modeling are used to show scientific pictures during science lessons	41	33	19	5	98	306	3.12	1.74	Accepted
2	Computer modeling are used in conveying historically concepts in science	52	20	16	10	98	310	3.16	1.73	Accepted
3	Computer modeling are used to give deeper understanding of scientific concepts ad teaching	53	26	10	9	98	319	3.25	1.75	Accepted
4	Computer modeling are used to explain thought concepts in science	57	20	15	6	98	324	3.30	1.73	Accepted
Grand mean (\bar{x})								3.21	1.74	Accepted

Source: Survey Data, 2024.

Table 2 Shows that item (1 to 4) have means of 3.12, 3.16, 3.25 and 3.30 respectively, which are greater than the criterion mean (2.50). Moreover, the grand mean (3.21) was also greater than the criterion means. This established that there is a high level of the extent of use of computer modeling in the teaching and learning of sciences in Ekeremor Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.

Research Question 3: To What extent are laboratory equipment used in the teaching and learning of sciences in Ekeremor Local Government Area of Bayelsa State?

Table 3 The mean and standard deviation on laboratory equipment used in the teaching and learning of sciences

S/N	ITEM	4 SA	3 A	2 D	1 SD	N	Total	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
1	Laboratory equipment are used in illustrating some experiences in science	61	14	12	11	98	321	3.27	1.76	Accepted
2	Laboratory equipment are used in demonstrating some scientific concepts	53	14	9	22	98	294	3	1.73	Accepted
3	Laboratory equipment are used to magnify and concretize theoretical complex concepts in teaching and learning	60	22	12	4	98	334	3.40	1.72	Accepted
Grand mean (\bar{x})								3.19	1.74	Accepted

Source: Survey Data, 2024.

Table 3 revealed that the items (1, 2, and 3) have means of 3.27, 3 and 3.40 respectively, which were greater than the criterion mean (2.50). Moreover, the grand mean (3.19) was also more than criterion mean. This revealed high extent of laboratory equipment used in the teaching and learning of sciences in Ekeremor Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.

Summary, Conclusions and Recommendations

The study on utilization of instructional simulation in the teaching and learning of sciences in senior secondary schools observed usage of graphics simulation in the teaching and learning of sciences at a very high extent. And that there is a high level of the extent of use of computer modeling in the teaching and learning of sciences, as well as high extent of laboratory equipment used in the teaching and learning of sciences in Ekeremor Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. It was held that the utilization of instructional simulation enhances teaching and learning of science. We strongly agree that simulations increase teachers’ and learners’ potential of discovering more knowledge and how to apply it. Consequently, the study strongly recommended a synergy in the usage of graphic simulation, computer modeling as well as laboratory equipment to enhance teaching and learning of science as to improve the students’ academic performance.

References

- Ali, Y. & De Jager, L. (2020). Connecting Life Sciences concepts to everyday life: A learner's perspective. WEI international Academic Conference Proceedings At: Boston, USA.
- Chen, C.H. & Howard, B. (2010). "Effect of live simulation on middle school students' attitudes and learning toward science," *Journal of Educational Technology & Society*, 13(1), 133–139.
- Chukundah, U.D. & Naade, N.B. (2020). Effect of computer animation instructional package on senior secondary school students' achievement in ecology in Emohua Rivers State. *International journal of innovative research and advance studies*, 9(2), 72-80.
- Chukundah, U.D. & Telima, A. (2020). Video-graphic multimedia instructional package and students' interest and achievement in biology in Rivers East Senatorial District. *International journal of innovative research and advance studies*, 8(1), 31-39.
- Esu, A. E. & Odetoyinbo, B. B. (2003). *Professional skills for Effective Teaching. Appraisal of Basic Issues in Educational Foundation*. Calabar: Rohoboth Favor Books.
- Esiobu, R. U. (2005). Promoting and Sustaining Educational Research for Self-Reliance. *International Journal of Educational Research and Administration*, 5(1), 1-11.
- Fallahi, C. R., Dell, M. L., Franz, J. A., & Greeley, K. A. H. (2017). Using Piaget's theory to enhance children's learning in science and math. In R. C. Clark (Ed.), *Learning and development: A Piagetian perspective* (147 - 164). New York: Routledge.
- Fape, O. O. (2007). Improvising Materials for Science Education in Nigerian Schools. A Paper Presented at the Workshop on Improvisation of Science Equipment.
- Folorunso, O. O. (2004). Relationship between some School and Teacher Variables and Students Achievement in Mathematics. *Journal of Science Teachers' Association of Nigeria* 35(17) 43-49.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004). *National Policy on Education*. Lagos: Heinemann Educational Books Ltd.
- Lateef, F. (2010). Simulation-based Learning: Just Like the Real Thing. *Journal of Emergencies Trauma and Shock*, 3(4), 348-52.
- Martinez-Jimenez, P., Pontes-Pedrajas, A. Polo, J. & Climent-Bellido, M.S. (2003). "Learning in chemistry with virtual laboratories," *Journal of Chemical Education*, 80(3),346–352.
- Memoir, J. (2016).The contribution of inductive methods in improving students' performance in biology subject in schools located in Bugesera district.
- Mohamed, A. H., Abdesselam, B.,Taoufik, H. & El Mehdi, A. (2021). The Effect of Using Computer Simulation on Students' Performance in Teaching and Learning Physics: Are There Any Gender and Area Gaps?
- Nwagbo, C. (2006). Effects of two teaching methods on the achievement in and attitude to biology of students of different levels of scientific literacy. *International Journal of Educational Research* 45(3), 216-229.
- Okebukola, P. A. O. (2015). Beyond the stereotype to New Trajectories in science teaching. Published by STAN. Printed by Taste and styles RH 13: Cultural Complex Abuja.
- Rutten, N., van Joolingen, W.R. & van der Veen, J.T. (2012).The learning effects of computer simulations in science education. *Journal of computer and education*, 58(1), 136-153.
- Sun, K., Lin, Y., & Yu, C. (2008). A study on learning effect among different learning styles in a Web-based lab of science for elementary school students. *Computers and Education*, 50(4), 1411–1422.